

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Spatial omics
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	28 - 29 October 2025
Time of event	1- 4:30pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Spatial omics provides unprecedented opportunities for the understanding of cells, tissues and systems by combining omics and imaging technologies.</p> <p>This hands-on workshop will show you how to analyse data from in situ spatial (e.g. CosMx, Xenium) experiments with Seurat in R to visualise gene expression within tissue samples. Using real-life experimental data we step through the process of reading in data, quality control, filtering, dimensionality reduction, visualisation and differential expression analysis. We will discuss the 'why' behind each step and essential best practices for designing and running spatial omics experiments.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two sessions.</p> <p>Sarah Williams and Fred Jaya led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then completed hands-on exercises giving them the chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>Facilitators provided assistance with exercises and answered questions in Slack in parallel to the main session</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the Training Materials section.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection. Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/spatial-omics-workshop-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 Spatial omics

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Audience	This workshop is for Australian researchers who have or will work on spatial transcriptomics data as part of their projects.
Prerequisites	<p>You should have basic knowledge of spatial omics technology - we recommend watching our introductory webinar Getting started with spatial omics.</p> <p>You should also have some familiarity with R. While you don't need to be an expert, being able to work with tables of data, load an R library and make basic plots (ideally with ggplot2) will help you get the most out of the workshop.</p>
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slack was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • Participants were provided with access to virtual machines running on ARDC Nectar Research Cloud. Packages, workflows and data were preinstalled.
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load CosMx data into a Seurat object and annotate it • Perform QC and filter the data for further analysis • Visualise tissues and gene expression • Perform PCA, UMAP and clustering analyses to group and visualise cells • Perform differential expression analysis
Lead Trainers	<p>Dr Sarah Williams, QCIF.</p> <p>Fred Jaya, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons</p>
Facilitators	<p>Dr Nicholas Matigian, QCIF</p> <p>Dr Ciccy Wang, Garvan Institute of Medical Research</p> <p>Dr Mitchell O'Brien, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons</p> <p>Dr Amarinder Singh Thind, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons</p>
Infrastructure provision	<p>Dr Giorgia Mori, Australian BioCommons</p> <p>Dr Mitchell O'Brien, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons</p>
Training materials	<p>Training materials including detailed notes, exercises and code: https://swbioinf.github.io/intro-spatial-transcriptomics-workshop/index.html</p> <p>Rmd files of R code used during the workshop via GitHub: https://github.com/swbioinf/intro-spatial-transcriptomics-workshop</p>

Related work	This workshop builds on our introductory webinar 'Getting started with spatial omics'. The training materials from this webinar can be found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/17096784